

A Study on the Effects of Leisure Activities on Smartphone Overdependence

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Abstract

In the modern information society, various information technologies provide many benefits to our lives. While the rapid development of information and communication technology provides us with various benefits, it is causing various side effects. The representative of these side effects is the overdependence on smartphones, which causes various problems such as health problems of modern people, maladjustment to social life, and poor academic performance. This study analyzes the effect of leisure activities on smartphone overdependence in Korea. For objective and accurate analysis, this study used statistical data of national-level smartphone overdependence surveys for the last 4 years provided by the National Information Society Agency. As a result of the analysis, it is found that the risk group of smartphone overdependence uses smartphones the most for leisure activities, while general users do rest the most. In addition, it is found that the risk group of overdependence hopes to use smartphones the most for leisure activities, while general users want to rest the most. On the other hand, it was found that there was no difference in satisfaction with leisure activities between the risk group of overdependence and general users. The results of this study hope to be a good basic study for preventing overdependence on smartphones in the future and preparing countermeasures.

Keywords: *smartphone overdependence, smartphone addiction, internet addiction, information and communication technology, smart technology*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the modern knowledge and information society, the use of various information and communication technologies and smart technologies is commonplace. In other words, modern people are becoming more abundant in their lives due to the use of the latest information and communication technologies and smart technologies, and their dependence on these technologies in various fields such as jobs, leisure, and social participation is increasing day by day. However, while the development of these technologies gives us various benefits, they are causing various side effects at the same time. Typical side effects include personal information infringement, copyright infringement, Internet addiction, and smartphones overdependence. Among these side effects, the problem of smartphones overdependence is becoming more serious day by day. With the popularization of mobile devices, smartphones are becoming a necessity for modern people.

According to the National Information Society Agency, the definition of smartphone overdependence is as follows [1]. Smartphone overdependence refers to a state in which the salience of smartphones increases due to excessive use of smartphones and the control of use decreases, thereby experiencing problematic results. Smartphone overdependence is composed of three factors: self-control failure, salience, and serious consequences. Specifically, the three factors can be explained in detail as follows.

①self-control failure

Lack of autonomous control over smartphone use compared to the user's subjective goals

②salience

The life pattern of using a smartphone in an individual's life is more prominent and the most important activity than other forms

③serious consequences

Continuous use of smartphones despite experiencing negative physical, psychological, and social consequences due to the use of smartphones

Meanwhile, according to the degree of overdependence on smartphones, it is classified into three groups as follows. Among the following three groups, high-risk groups and potential risk groups are classified as risk groups of smartphone overdependence.

①high-risk group

A state in which interpersonal conflicts, daily role problems, health problems, etc. have occurred seriously due to the loss of control over the use of smartphones

②potential risk group

A stage in which interpersonal conflicts or problems with daily roles begin to occur while the control over smartphone use is weakened

③general user group

A state of using a smartphone in a controlled form

According to recent statistics from the National Information Society Agency, more than 20% of the entire population is classified as a smartphone overdependence risk group. Specifically, 23.3% in 2020, 24.2% in 2021, 23.6% in 2022, and 23.1% in 2023 [1,2,3,4]. Therefore, smartphone overdependence is not only an individual-level problem, but also a very important social and national problem, and prevention and healing of smartphone overdependence are emerging as tasks that must be solved at the national level.

A wide variety of causes are working with each other on smartphone overdependence. It is a difficult task to clearly identify the cause of smartphone overdependence. This study analyzes the relationship between leisure activities and smartphone overdependence. In other words, it is intended to analyze the effect of leisure activities on the risk group and general user group. For this purpose, statistical data for the last four years at the national level provided by the National Information Society Agency were used.

2. Related Works

Various studies on smartphone overdependence in Korea are as follows.

In Hur's study, the effect of leisure-seeking smartphone use on academic enthusiasm was analyzed longitudinally in the upper grades of elementary school and middle school students [5]. The analysis results are as follows. First, in the fourth grade of elementary school and the first year of middle school, it was found that the use of leisure-seeking smartphones had a direct negative effect on academic enthusiasm, and there was a partial mediating relationship that had an effect through

each of smartphone dependence and social contraction. In addition, it was found that there was a sequential double mediating effect that had an effect by sequentially passing through smartphone dependence and social contraction. Second, the factors that influence the rate of decreasing academic enthusiasm as the grade goes up were the use of leisure-seeking smartphones and the degree of dependence on smartphones in the fourth grade of elementary school and the first grade of middle school. On the other hand, it was found that the rate of change of each variable did not affect the rate of decrease in academic enthusiasm.

In Oh and his colleagues' study, the effect of leisure activities of single-parent families on the overdependence of middle and high school students on smartphones through the depression of parents and the controlled mediating effect according to the child's gender were investigated [6]. As a result of the analysis, the leisure activities of single-parent families did not directly affect the overdependence of middle and high school students on smartphones. On the other hand, the leisure activities of single-parent families affected the overdependence of middle and high school students on smartphones through the mediation of parents' depression. In other words, the leisure activities of single-parent families lowered the level of depression of parents, followed by the level of overdependence of children on smartphones. In addition, there was a difference according to the gender of children in the mediating effect of parental depression. Specifically, the mediating effect of the leisure activities of single-parent families on lowering the overdependence on smartphones of middle and high school students through the depression of parents was more pronounced in male children than in female children.

In a study by Jeon and his colleagues, the relationship between parental attitude and behavior, friendship, media education, leisure life and smartphone overdependence among the microsystem variables surrounding adolescents was explored, and the mediating effect of smartphone usage time was verified in the relationship between the microsystem variables and the adolescents' overdependence on smartphones [7]. The analysis results were as follows. First, adolescents who thought that their parents' interest was high were less dependent on smartphones than adolescents who did not. The adolescents who perceived the restrictive intervention of their parents highly showed higher overdependence on smartphones, and the active intervention of parents did not show a significant relationship with the overdependence on smartphones. In addition, the adolescents who perceived their parents' level of smartphone use higher were more dependent on smartphones. Second, adolescents with close online friendships were more dependent on smartphones than adolescents who did not, but offline friendships did not show a significant relationship with smartphone overdependence. Third, adolescents with media education experience were less dependent on smartphones than adolescents who did not. Fourth, adolescents' leisure life had a significant negative relationship with smartphone overdependence. Fifth, smartphone usage time was found to negatively mediate the relationship between parents' active intervention and media education and smartphone overdependence, and the relationship between parents' smartphone use level, online friendship, and leisure life and smartphone overdependence.

In Bae's study, the effects of smartphone usage types and excessive expectations for smartphones on adolescents' smartphone overdependence were verified [8]. The analysis results are as follows. Age and household income negatively affected smartphone overdependence. The weekly usage time of smartphones positively affected problematic use, a sub-factor of smartphone overdependence. The use of smartphones for leisure did not affect the overdependence on smartphones, but

negatively affected problematic use, a sub-factor of smartphone overdependence. The use of smartphones for messengers did not affect smartphone overdependence. On the other hand, the use of messengers positively affected salience, a sub-factor of smartphone overdependence, and negatively affected problematic use.

In Kim's study, the factors influencing smartphone overdependence and life satisfaction by smartphone use type were analyzed [9]. As a result of the analysis, smartphone overdependence occurred in the leisure-seeking type and the information-seeking type. On the other hand, the communication type reduced the overdependence on the smartphone. The type of smartphone use that had the greatest influence on life satisfaction was the communication type. It was found that the longer the smartphone usage time and the higher the overdependence on the smartphone, the more negatively the life satisfaction was.

Chi and Lee's study analyzed the mediating effect of social withdrawal in the effect of parents' negative parenting attitude on the overdependence on leisure-seeking smartphones of second-grade middle school students [10]. The results of the study are as follows. First, it was found that parents' negative parenting attitude had an effect on adolescents' overdependence on leisure-seeking smartphones, and the higher the level of negative parenting attitude, the higher the level of overdependence on leisure-seeking smartphones of adolescents. Second, in the effect of parents' negative parenting attitude on adolescents' overdependence on leisure-seeking smartphones, there is a partial mediating effect of social withdrawal, which can be interpreted that parents' negative parenting attitude increases the level of social withdrawal of adolescents, thereby increasing the level of overdependence on leisure-seeking smartphones.

Han and Chang's study analyzed the structural relationship between a series of ecological variables such as mobile Internet usage time, smartphone dependence, leisure activities, and family ritual experiences [11]. The results are as follows. First, as a result of correlation analysis, it was found that children with late birth order and children from dual-income families used more mobile devices. Second, it was predicted that the more family leisure activities, the lower the level of overdependence on smartphones for children through mobile device usage time. Third, it was predicted that the increase in family consciousness experience would reduce overdependence on smartphones by mediating a decrease in mobile device usage time.

Lee and Kim's research found out the changes in leisure activities of adolescents due to COVID-19 and analyzed the relationship between changes in leisure activities, leisure satisfaction, and overdependence on smartphones [12]. As a result, leisure activities participated before and after COVID-19 showed significant differences according to gender, and participated in hobbies and relaxation activities after COVID-19. As a result of surveying the satisfaction level of leisure activities, the emotional satisfaction was the highest and the physical satisfaction was the lowest. In addition, in the case of overdependence on smartphones, the ratio of the potential risk overdependence group was high, and the smartphone usage time of female students was significantly higher than that of male students. As a result of examining the difference between leisure satisfaction and the distribution of overdependence on smartphones according to changes in leisure activities, there was no significant difference, but adolescents who participated in hobby entertainment activities for a long time tended to have a high proportion of the potential risk overdependence group.

3. Materials and Methods

In this study, for objective and fair smartphone overdependence analysis, statistical data from the last 4 years(2020-2023) conducted at the national level by the National Information Society Agency(<http://www.nia.or.kr>) were used [1,2,3,4]. Since 2004, the agency has investigated and announced the status of Koreans' overdependence on the Internet and smartphones. The subjects of the survey were smartphone(Internet) users aged 3 to 69 within 10,000 households nationwide(who used more than once within the last month), and the household visit interview survey was adopted as the survey method.

As of 2023, the most recent statistical data, 22,844 people from 10,000 households nationwide participated in the survey. By subject, 6.3% of infants(3-9 years old), 8.7% of adolescents(10-19 years old), 66.1% of adults(20-59 years old), and 19.0% of those in their 60s(60-69 years old) participated. In addition, by age, 6.3% of 3-9 years old, 8.7% of teenagers, 9.4% of 20s, 21.8% of 30s, 17.0% of 40s, 17.0% of 50s, 17.9% of 50s, and 19.0% of 60s participated. Meanwhile, 48.0% of men and 52.0% of women participated in the survey. The survey period is from September 2023 to November 2023, and the sampling error is $\pm 0.50\%$ (95% of confidence level). Statistical surveys for other years are also conducted similarly to 2023, so specific numerical data and ratios are omitted.

On the other hand, in this study, statistical data on smartphone overdependence published annually by the National Information Society Agency were used, and statistical data can be used by anyone through appropriate citation. Additionally, all statistical data on smartphone dependence are anonymized, so ethical consent, such as consent to process and use personal information, is not required for the survey subjects.

Statistical data collected in this study were analyzed using the SPSS(Statistical Package for the Social Science) package software. ANOVA(variable analysis) and t-test(verification) were adopted to accurately analyze the state of overdependence on smartphones. In addition, Scheffe's test was adopted for post-verification in this study.

4. Findings and Analysis

4.1. The Current Status of Smartphone Overdependence

In this section, we introduce the status of smartphone overdependence in Korea.

In particular, we introduce the status of overdependence related to leisure activities focused in this study.

First, Table 1 shows the main leisure activities of the smartphone overdependence risk group and general users by year.

Table 1. Main Leisure Activities of Smartphone Users by Year

Year	User group	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8
2020	Risk group	37.0	21.6	13.1	6.2	9.2	8.7	4.1	
	General user	29.9	40.4	12.2	9.3	8.0	5.2	4.6	
2021	Risk group	34.5	23.7	13.9	8.9	8.8	7.3	2.8	
	General user	26,6	32.6	12.6	9.3	9.1	6.5	3.2	

2022	Risk group	38,3	16,6	11,2	5,5	8,9	16,2	3,3	0,0
	General user	25,3	33,6	12,9	7,2	7,4	8,3	5,3	0,1
2023	Risk group	46,8	16,4	9,5	5,1	9,4	9,3	3,5	0,0
	General user	27,8	36,1	10,8	10,1	5,9	5,1	4,2	0,0

(Unit: %)

Where A1: Smartphone use, A2: Rest, A3: Hobbies and entertainment activities, A4: Social and related activities, A5: Watching and participating in sports, A6: Viewing and participating in culture and arts, A7: Tourism activities, A8: others

Meanwhile, Table 2 shows the desired leisure activities of the smartphone overdependence risk group and general users by year

Table 2. Desired Leisure Activities of Smartphone Users

Year	User group	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8
2020	Risk group	21.2	14.1	14.5	9.1	11.7	19.0	10.0	
	General user	12.0	27.1	14.4	10.2	10.5	13.5	12.0	
2021	Risk group	19.6	19.5	14.6	10.4	13.0	14.1	8.8	
	General user	14.8	22.5	13.6	11.3	13.7	13.3	10.8	
2022	Risk group	17.3	11.9	16.6	7.7	13.6	22.7	10.2	0.0
	General user	10.5	20.6	15.1	9.7	11.9	17.0	15.1	0.1
2023	Risk group	19.0	13.4	14.4	7.4	15.3	18.1	12.1	0.1
	General user	10.2	21.3	14.9	10.6	12.1	15.9	15.0	0.1

(Unit: %)

Where A1: Smartphone use, A2: Rest, A3: Hobbies and entertainment activities, A4: Social and related activities, A5: Watching and participating in sports, A6: Viewing and participating in culture and arts, A7: Tourism activities, A8: others

On the other hand, the following Table 3 shows the actual state of satisfaction with leisure activities of smartphone users.

Table 3. State of Satisfaction with Leisure Activities of Smartphone Users

Year	User group	Satisfaction ratio
2020	Risk group	64.6
	General user	55.6
2021	Risk group	64.7
	General user	60.6
2022	Risk group	62.9
	General user	69.5
2023	Risk group	69.2
	General user	68.7

(Unit: %)

4.2. Analysis Results of Smartphone Overdependence

In this section, we introduce the results of analyzing statistical data introduced in Section 4.1.

First, Table 4 shows the analysis results of the main leisure activities of the smartphone overdependence risk group and general users.

Table 4. Analysis of Main Leisure Activities of Smartphone Users

Activity Type	Risk group		General User		Overall		F	p
	Man	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
A1	39.15	5.34	27.40	1.95	33.28	7.30	20.15***	0.000
A2	19.58	3.65	35.68	3.48	27.63	9.22		
A3	11.93	1.97	12.13	0.93	12.03	1.43		
A4	6.43	1.71	8.98	1.24	7.70	1.94		
A5	9.08	0.28	7.60	1.33	8.34	1.19		
A6	10.38	3.97	6.28	1.49	8.33	3.54		
A7	3.43	0.54	4.33	0.88	3.88	0.83		
A8	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.07	0.03	0.05		

*** $p < 0.001$

(Unit: %)

Where A1: Smartphone use, A2: Rest, A3: Hobbies and entertainment activities, A4: Social and related activities, A5: Watching and participating in sports, A6: Viewing and participating in culture and arts, A7: Tourism activities, A8: others

Looking at the main leisure activities, the average of smartphone use of the overdependence risk group was the highest at 39.15%, followed by 19.58% for rest, 11.93% for hobbies and entertainment activities, 10.38% for viewing and participating in culture and arts, and 9.08% for watching and participating in sports, while the average of rest of general users was the highest at 35.68%, followed by 27.40% for smartphone use, 12.13% for hobbies and entertainment activities, 8.98% for social and related activities, and 7.60% for watching and participating in sports, showing a statistically significant difference ($F=20.15$, $p < 0.0001$). Therefore, it can be seen that the overdependence risk group uses smartphones the most for leisure activities, while general users use rest the most.

Next, Table 5 shows the analysis results of the desired leisure activities of the smartphone dependence risk group and general users.

Table 5. Analysis of the Desired Leisure Activities of Smartphone Users

Activity Type	Risk group		General User		Overall		F	p
	Man	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
A1	19.28	1.61	11.88	2.10	15.58	4.32	10.92***	0.000
A2	14.73	3.31	22.88	2.92	18.80	5.23		
A3	15.03	1.05	14.50	0.67	14.76	0.86		
A4	8.65	1.38	10.45	0.68	9.55	1.39		
A5	13.40	1.49	12.05	1.31	12.73	1.49		

A6	18.48	3.53	14.93	1.82	16.70	3.22		
A7	10.28	1.36	13.23	2.16	11.75	2.30		
A8	0.05	0.07	0.10	0.00	0.08	0.05		

*** $p < .001$

(Unit: %)

Where A1: Smartphone use, A2: Rest, A3: Hobbies and entertainment activities, A4: Social and related activities, A5: Watching and participating in sports, A6: Viewing and participating in culture and arts, A7: Tourism activities, A8: others

Looking at the desired leisure activities, the average of smartphone use for the overdependence risk group was the highest at 19.28%, followed by 18.48% for viewing and participating in culture and arts, 15.03% for hobbies and entertainment activities, 14.73% for rest, and 13.40% for watching and participating in sports, while the average of rest for general users was the highest at 22.88%, followed by 14.93% for viewing and participating in culture and arts, 14.50% for hobbies and entertainment activities, 13.23% for tourism activities, 12.05% for watching and participating in sports, and 11.88% for smartphone use, showing a statistically significant difference ($F=10.92$, $p < 0.0001$). Therefore, it can be seen that the risk group of overdependence wants to use smartphones the most for leisure activities, while general users want to rest the most.

Table 6 shows the analysis results of the satisfaction with leisure activities for the risk group and general users of smartphone overdependence.

Table 6. Analysis of Satisfaction with Leisure Activities of Smartphone Users

User group	Mean	SD	t	p
Risk group	65.35	2.70	0.49	0.644
General user	63.60	6.68		

Looking at the satisfaction level of leisure activities, the average of the overdependence risk group was 65.35, higher than the average of 63.60 for general users, but there was no statistically significant difference. Therefore, it can be seen that there is no difference in satisfaction with leisure activities between the overdependence risk group and general users.

5. DISCUSSIONS

The analysis results in Chapter 4 can be interpreted as follows.

First, Table 4 shows the analysis results of main leisure activities of smartphone users. As a result of the analysis, the smartphone overdependence risk group had the highest use of smartphones in their main leisure activities, while the general user group had the highest rest activity. This is because the general user group enjoys rest time as a leisure activity, while the overdependence risk group enjoys smartphone use, and it is necessary to induce alternative leisure activities instead of the smartphone use of the smartphone overdependence risk group.

On the other hand, Table 5 shows the analysis results of the desired leisure activities of smartphone users. As a result of the analysis, it was found that in the overdependence risk group, the desired leisure activity was the highest in smartphone use, while the rest activity was the highest in the general user group.

This means that the smartphone overdependence risk group is interested in smartphone use whenever they have time and is actually using a smartphone. As in the results of Table 4, it is necessary to induce leisure activities of the smartphone overdependence risk group to a healthy form of activity other than smartphone use, especially through rest activities.

Meanwhile, Table 6 shows that there was no statistically significant difference in the satisfaction of leisure activities between the smartphone overdependence risk group and the general user group. This means that the two groups are receiving the same satisfaction in leisure activities. In other words, it can be interpreted that there is no difference in satisfaction when the overdependence risk group is converted to the general user group. Therefore, if the leisure activities of the overdependence risk group are induced from the use of smartphones to the rest activities, the same satisfaction can be obtained, thereby further justifying the necessity of converting the leisure activities of the overdependence risk group.

In order to solve the problem of overdependence on smartphones in terms of leisure activities, it is fundamentally necessary to induce healthy leisure activities for smartphone users. In particular, for general users, various and sound leisure activities should be induced through education to prevent overdependence on smartphones. On the other hand, for the smartphone overdependence risk group, education or publicity that can be replaced with smartphone use should be strengthened as a healing activity.

On the other hand, the reason why the main leisure activity and the desired leisure activity are different is that more than 50% of all respondents answered 'there is not enough time' [1]. In addition, according to Table 5, the risk group of smartphone overdependence said that about 20% of all respondents wanted to use a smartphone as a desired leisure activity. In other words, about 80% of the risk group of smartphone overdependence said they wished for leisure activities other than using a smartphone. However, since other leisure activities cannot be enjoyed due to lack of time, it is very important to induce the risk group of smartphone overdependence to have time in their lives.

6. Conclusions

In the modern information society, modern people enjoy various benefits in their daily lives thanks to various information technologies and smart technologies. While these technologies are expected to have more impact on our lives in the future, these technologies are causing various side effects that we do not want or expect. Among these side effects, the representative one is the overdependence on smartphones. This is because smartphone is becoming a necessity with the popularization of smartphones.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the relationship between smartphone overdependence and leisure activity. Specifically, smartphone users were classified into an overdependence risk group and a general user group, and the main leisure activities and desired leisure activities were analyzed statistically and significantly for these two groups. In addition, the satisfaction of these two groups for leisure activities was analyzed. For this analysis, official statistical data at the national level for the last 4 years were collected and analyzed.

The analysis results are as follows. First, in terms of main leisure activities, the smartphone overdependence risk group had the highest smartphone use, while the general user group had the highest rest activity. Second, in terms of desired leisure activities, the risk group for overdependence had the highest smartphone use, while the general user group had the highest rest activity. Third, there was no statistically

significant difference between the smartphone overdependence risk group and the general user group in terms of leisure activity satisfaction.

This study focused on quantitative research on the relationship analysis between leisure activities and smartphone overdependence, and failed to consider various variables. Therefore, as a follow-up study, first, it is necessary to investigate the effect of leisure activities on smartphone dependence more specifically by considering various variables in leisure activities. In addition, it is necessary to analyze qualitative factors through in-depth interviews on the risk group of smartphone overdependence.

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